

WORLD EXPERIENCE AND THE ROLE OF DATA JOURNALISM IN THE FIGHT AGAINST FALSE INFORMATION

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Abstract. *Today, we live in a time where it is difficult to distinguish false information from the truth. In a world of hyper-information, it is difficult for the average reader to distinguish accuracy, truth, professional ethics, transparency, pluralism and credibility. Separating fact from fiction is becoming a problem, especially in the age of artificial intelligence. What are the topics, form, presented format, content creation research of the media products being created in Uzbekistan? Can it meet the demands of modern journalism? What forms of data projects are found in Uzbekistan today.*

Keywords: *hyper-information, blog, deepfake, fake-news, disinformation, infographics, data projects.*

In November 2022, the "ChatGPT" program appeared, and a new obstacle appeared in front of journalism. Recently, deepfakes in the name of the President and some officials began to appear on social networks in Uzbekistan. In cyberspace, cases of falsification of a person's photo, voice and other biometric data using special programs are called deepfakes. Uzbekistan is also considering determining responsibility for the distribution of such fabricated information that appeared on the Internet. It is not surprising that there are various articles related to discrediting a person or posting false information about him.

The leading countries of the world are making various decisions and reforms to prevent false information, disinformation, "fake news", identify their harm and combat them. For example, in early May 2018, Belgian Minister Alexander De Croo announced two initiatives aimed at preventing the spread of disinformation online. First, the government formed an expert panel of journalists and scientists to propose potential solutions by June 25, 2018. Second, he launched a dedicated website to alert people to misinformation and introduced a Reddit-style way to allow people to vote up and down government proposals.

In January 2019, The Cambodia newspaper reported that the government had launched a live TV program investigating disinformation. This was also a special fight against false information. China has some of the strictest laws in the world when it comes to disinformation. In 2016, the government will criminalize the creation or dissemination of rumors "undermining the economic and social order", reports Foreign.

Another law passed in 2017 required social media platforms to only republish and link to news articles from registered media outlets. This also helped more or less in the fight against disinformation.

In late August 2018, the Chinese government launched an app that allows people to report potential. According to Reuters, it has accounts on platforms such as Weibo, which also uses

artificial intelligence to automatically detect rumors, and WeChat, the app, through which it has broadcast state media messages.

On June 14, 2018, MPs passed controversial amendments to Belarus' "Media Laws" that would allow the government to prosecute those who spread false information online. One lawmaker said the law, which also allows blocking of social networks and other websites if violations are found, is aimed at protecting citizens' rights and strengthening government information security.

A Media Wise study conducted by the Poynter Institute found that one-third of teenagers today are exposed to false information on the Internet every day... Only twelve percent of teens are capable of spotting fake news... So the remaining eighty-eight percent are of any kind. and will blindly believe the seemingly false news.

What is Chat GPT? It is a powerful artificial intelligence technology that can spread misinformation and create confusion in society. Earlier, a video was released showing Ukrainian President Volodymyr Zelensky ordering his troops to lay down their weapons and surrender. It spread all over Ukraine, and hackers even posted it on a Ukrainian news agency.

This is an example of a "deepfake" - a video where a person's face or body is digitally manipulated to make it look like they said or did something they didn't. quickly noticed that it looked a little odd. But if you don't notice that it is deeply fake, it can cause serious damage. But it is important to recognize its limitations.

If you're trying to figure out if what you're reading is created by artificial intelligence, ask yourself three questions:

1. Who is behind the data?
2. What is the evidence?
3. What do other sources say?

Now is the age of data journalism... In the world of hyper-information, reliability, independence, accuracy, professional ethics, transparency and pluralism are the values that confirm relations with the public. Data journalism is the most reliable source because it is an analytical view of various numbers and facts.

In order to combat disinformation in the conditions of Uzbekistan, it is necessary to consider and propose several issues:

1. Providing information: providing fair and complete information so that citizens can make the right political choices;
2. Investigation: the study of concentrated sources of power, particularly government power;
3. Analysis: providing a coherent interpretive framework to help citizens understand a complex world;
4. Social Empathy: Tell people about others in their community and world so they can appreciate other people's perspectives and lives, especially those less privileged than themselves;
5. Public forum: provides a space for dialogue between citizens through pluralistic and interdisciplinary approaches to issues and serves as a common carrier of the views of different groups in society;
6. Mobilization: (as appropriate) serving as advocates for political programs and perspectives and mobilizing people to act in support of those programs without compromising standards of scrutiny and the public interest.

As a result, it can be difficult to determine whether online videos have been digitally altered or whether information surrounding certain images is false.

The fight against false information is not only within the framework of the government and its decisions and laws, but it is also the basis for carrying out educational activities among the population and fighting against disinformation in the civil society.

But here are some tips to help you spot the videos that are usually scamming you:

1. Always try to find the original source of the material. Before you trust what you're seeing, use a keyword search to see if a video has been altered or not, and read more.

2. A video that appears to have unintelligible, awkward gaps may be questionable and edited.

3. If you see a public figure doing something that is exaggerated, unrealistic, or out of character, it could be deeply fake.

Conclusion

Therefore, it is necessary to immediately develop the necessary decisions, laws, and normative documents to combat "fake" news, "deepfake" materials and disinformation in Uzbekistan. Otherwise, problems may arise among the population during the election process in the future.

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